

Mixed Methods Analysis of Turnover Intention Drivers among AMN Surabaya Employees

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ABSTRACT

Employee turnover can have negative impacts. The presence of turnover intention indicates employee dissatisfaction. From 2023 to 2025, the turnover intention among Asrama Mahasiswa Nusantara (AMN0 Surabaya employees gradually increased. This is can be driven by workplace conflict, work overload, job embeddedness, and moderated by work environment, undermining organizational loyalty. Therefore, in this study a mixed methods approach was used to analyzes factors influencing turnover intention among organic employees at Asrama Mahasiswa Nusantara (AMN) Surabaya. The methods used included a survey of 44 respondents, and in-depth interviews with observations of 3 active employees and 3 former employees. Quantitative data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis for qualitative insights. The results of the study showed that workplace conflict, excessive workload, and job attachment did not have a significant influence on the turnover intention. However, work environment fails to moderate these relationships. The implications of this research are strengthening trust, clarify bureaucracy, balance task assignments, and implement performance-based rewards to enhance motivation and reduce turnover intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Intergenerational job competition is currently a major challenge for the workforce, as the modern era is also characterized by increased education and limited job opportunities. Amidst these conditions, employee sustainability and retention are critical issues for organizations, including government agencies. One institution experiencing these dynamics is the Nusantara Student Dormitory (AMN) Surabaya. AMN Surabaya is a new institution established based on Presidential Regulation No. 106 of 2021 and inaugurated on November 29, 2022. The Nusantara Student Dormitory (AMN) Surabaya plays a strategic role as a character-building and soft-skills development institution for undergraduate and graduate scholarship students studying at four (4) state universities in Surabaya. These students come from all 38 provinces in Indonesia, with diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds.

AMN employees have a significant responsibility to create a conducive environment for the dormitory's residents. Employee status within the AMN Surabaya organizational structure is divided into organic and non-organic employees.

Organic employees include the daily management of AMN Surabaya, along with the caretaker and administrative staff. Non-organic employees, or seconded personnel, come from the Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI) and the Indonesian National Police (POLRI). Since its inception, AMN Surabaya has experienced significant workforce dynamics, particularly in the high turnover rate of organic employees.

From the start of operations in 2022 to 2025, the number of organic employees fluctuated by 10%, from 42 to 38 in 2023. Three and one employee resigned in 2024 and 2025, respectively, with a remaining turnover rate of 12% to 34% from now until 2026.

Various factors that may contribute to turnover intention among AMN employees include work conflict, work overload, and job embeddedness, which create a stressful work environment. Work conflict is primarily triggered by uneven workload. Work overload in some work units, although balanced with equal compensation, does not take into account the workload and responsibilities associated with the position. The stressful work environment also stems

from the social problems of its occupants, so AMN employees are constantly challenged to resolve their problems.

Various studies show that job stress and job satisfaction are highly correlated with employee commitment and will influence employees' decisions about whether to continue or quit a job (Karsh et al., 2005; Mahdi et al., 2012; Alam and Asim, 2019). According to Hakro et al. (2022), work overload has positive and significant relationships with employee turnover intentions, job satisfaction, employee engagement, and job stress. Factors such as work overload and role conflict have a positive relationship with turnover intention (Chen et al., 2011), and Sheraz et al. (2014) identified a positive effect of role conflict on stress. Takawira et al. (2014) revealed significant relationships between job embeddedness, work engagement, and turnover intention.

The work environment in the AMN dormitory affects employee job satisfaction and, in turn, turnover intention. This study aims to uncover factors influencing turnover intention among AMN Surabaya employees using a mixed-methods approach based on phenomena and in-depth interview observations. This study aims to understand how human resource assets can optimize employee management to minimize turnover intentions, which negatively impact the institution's sustainability. This research is expected to provide insight into human resource asset management and contribute to the development of human resource policies in the workplace.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Turnover Intention

Intention to quit refers to an employee's tendency to resign from their job. It is a cognitive process that reflects an individual's desire to voluntarily leave their current workplace and seek alternative employment (Zeffane in Halimah et al., 2016). According to Kumar (2011), turnover is a critical human resource issue in all sectors which affects productivity and service quality. High levels of intention to quit often reflect employee dissatisfaction with the position they are assigned by the organization or institution. This dissatisfaction can stem from several factors, such as equal pay despite unequal responsibilities, unequal work assignments, lack of recognition for achievements, and lack of appreciation or perceived lack of appreciation in the work environment.

B. Work Environment

The work environment encompasses all physical and non-physical aspects surrounding employees, including equipment, materials, work methods, work arrangements, social relationships, organizational policies, and culture, which influence employee behavior and performance (Sedarmayanti, 2015; Surnoyoto, 2015; Sunyoto, 2015). The physical work environment encompasses the actual conditions of the workplace such as desks, chairs, lighting,

temperature, cleanliness, noise levels, and wall color which directly or indirectly influence work comfort and productivity (Sedarmayanti, 2018). Meanwhile, the non-physical work environment encompasses socio-psychological conditions, relationships with superiors and coworkers, organizational culture, and applicable policies and procedures. According to (Mangkunegara, 2017), a conducive work environment is an important factor in shaping employee comfort, motivation, morale, and effectiveness in carrying out daily tasks, while reducing work stress. Conversely, a poor work environment can cause stress, reduce productivity, and increase intentions to leave the job. Some indicators of a non-physical work environment, proposed by (Sedarmayanti, 2011), include: (1) relationships between employees and supervisors characterized by mutual respect and appreciation, and (2) positive co-worker relationships within a team that foster a harmonious climate and enhance performance. Fath (2015) further identifies the following indicators: clear and structured work procedures, job standards, supervisor accountability, task clarity, and a reward system that recognizes employee achievement and initiative.

C. Job Embeddedness

Job embeddedness is a psychological construct that describes the overall strength that binds individuals to their current job and organization, thereby reducing their likelihood of leaving (Mitchell et al., 2001). It emphasizes the interaction of social, emotional, and economic factors that create a sense of attachment and retention. From a social learning perspective inspired by Bandura, this attachment can be seen as a form of learned loyalty, formed through repeated interactions, role modeling, and identification with the work environment. Job embeddedness is typically operationalized through three core indicators: (1) sacrifice – the perceived loss of benefits and relationships resulting from leaving the organization; (2) fit – the perceived compatibility and comfort with the job and work environment; and (3) relatedness – the presence of social support and networks at work that bind employees to the organization. According to Pekasa et al. (2018), higher levels of job embeddedness are associated with stronger loyalty, commitment, and productivity, as well as lower turnover intentions, because the perceived costs of leaving a job outweigh the anticipated benefits of change.

D. Work Overload

Work overload is defined as a condition in which an individual is given work tasks or responsibilities that exceed their physical, mental, or temporal capacity to achieve optimal completion (Ayu, 2022). Scientific perspectives on work overload include identifying causal factors, its multidimensional impact on individuals and organizations, and implementing effective mitigation strategies (Bari & Hidayat, 2022). This can be said that high workload can cause fatigue effects for employees both physically and

mentally (Saputri & Rini, 2024). Theoretically, work overload is often linked to Maslow Hierarchy of Needs, where workplace conflict acts as a barrier to the fulfillment of social and self-esteem needs. This occurs by creating interpersonal tensions that exacerbate psychological stress and increase intentions to quit. Within the framework of the Job Demands-Control model, high job demands coupled with low autonomy significantly increase the risk of professional burnout and emotional exhaustion. Furthermore, based on Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, repeated punitive actions (punishment) can reduce employee motivation and lower self-efficacy he internal belief in one's ability to perform tasks successfully under challenging circumstances. According to (Gibson, 2009), the main determinants of work overload include: Time Pressure: Constraints requiring task completion within a limited timeframe. Work Schedule: Long working hours or a busy schedule that leads to a buildup of tasks. Role Conflict and Ambiguity: Lack of role clarity or conflicting demands that cause cognitive dissonance. Information Overload: The need to process excessive volumes of data simultaneously. Repetitive Tasks: Monotonous activities that accelerate physical and mental fatigue. High Responsibility: Significant accountability burdens in professional roles. Environmental Stress: Suboptimal workplace conditions, such as excessive noise or physical discomfort. Furthermore, Puteri (2024) identified the main indicators of work overload as: (1) target achievement requirements, (2) prevailing working conditions, (3) rigid performance standards, (4) time allocation inefficiencies, and (5) workloads that exceed individual capacity. In conclusion, chronic workload negatively impacts employee health, manifesting in stress and fatigue, which increase the likelihood of work-related errors. Consequently, this leads to decreased motivation, lower job satisfaction, and decreased organizational productivity. Effective management through task restructuring, realistic scheduling, and improved organizational communication is crucial to maintaining optimal performance without compromising employee well-being (Ayu, 2022; Schultz, 1998; Gibson, 2009).

E. Work Conflict

Within organizational dynamics, conflict is viewed as a natural social occurrence; therefore, conflict management seeks to navigate these tensions effectively to foster positive outcomes while reducing negative effects on organizational stability (Rahim, 2001). The main factors contributing to work conflict include individual variations in values and emotions, different cultural backgrounds, and conflicting interests among stakeholders (Mangkunegara, 2017; Wirawan, 2009). In practical terms, work conflict is identified by several significant indicators: Communication Barriers: Breakdowns in understanding or information sharing. Goal Incongruence: Differences in

objectives between parties. Perceptual Differences: Discrepancies in how situations or actions are interpreted.

III. METHOD

This study used a mixed methods approach, integrating quantitative data managed through PLS-SEM analysis and qualitative data managed through thematic analysis to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between variables while deepening the interpretation of the underlying phenomena in the field. Quantitative data were collected using a saturated sampling method, a method of selecting respondents for a small population (<100) by taking all available respondents/population (Ahmed, 2024). All the Nusantara Student Dormitory (AMN) Surabaya employees (44 respondents) completed the questionnaire and three (3) respondents were interviewed as employees who had turnover intentions. The main variables studied include work conflict (X₁), work overload (X₂), work engagement (X₃), work environment as a moderating variable (Z), and intention to quit (Y). Qualitative data was used to deepen understanding of the phenomena occurring in the field. Qualitative data consists of descriptive data containing written or spoken words from a person and observable behaviour.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results

A. Analysis of PLS Result

Table 1. R Square of Turnover Intention of AMN Employees

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Turnover Intention (Y)	0.558	0.487

The R-square value indicates the extent to which the exogenous variables explain the variability of the endogenous variable. In this study, the R-square for turnover intention (Y) is 0.558, meaning that the exogenous constructs Job Embeddedness (X₃), Work Conflict (X₁), Work Overload (X₂), and Work Environment (Z) collectively explain 55.8% of the variance in turnover intention, while the remaining 44.2% is influenced by factors outside the model. The adjusted R-square value of 0.487 provides a more conservative estimate, indicating that approximately 48.7% of the variance is explained by the model after accounting for the number of variables. Overall, the model demonstrates moderate explanatory power in capturing the relationship between the exogenous variables and turnover intention (Y). In addition, predictive relevance is assessed through Q-square (Q²). With Q² = 0.558, the model explains 55.8% of the variance in the data, while 44.2% remains attributable to external factors. A Q² value above the minimum threshold (>0) indicates moderate predictive relevance, suggesting that the model is capable of

effectively predicting the endogenous variable even though other unmodeled factors still influence the data.

B. Analysis of PLS Models

Figure 1. Structural Model Evaluation with p-Value of X, Z and Y Variables

To determine whether a hypothesis is accepted or rejected, the p-value is interpreted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%). If the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, indicating a significant effect. Conversely, if the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, indicating no significant effect. Figure 1 showed that Work Conflict (X1), Work Overload (X2), Job Embeddedness (X3) have coefficient of 0.053, 0.257, -0.251 respectively. Meanwhile, Work Environment x Work Conflict and Work Environment x Work Overload have coefficient relationships of -0.191 and -0.125.

C. Hypothesis Testing Result

Table 2. Result of Structural Model Evaluation for Testing Hypothesis

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Conflict (X1) -> Turnover Intention (Y)	0.053	0.060	0.179	0.299	0.765
Work Overload (X2) -> Turnover Intention (Y)	0.257	0.298	0.165	1.559	0.119

Job Embeddedness (X3) -> Turnover Intention (Y)	-0.251	0.229	0.173	1.449	0.147
Work Environment (Z) x Work Conflict (X1) -> Turnover Intention (Y)	-0.191	0.74	0.178	1.071	0.284
Work Environment (Z) x Work Overload (X2) -> Turnover Intention (Y)	-0.125	0.145	0.219	0.572	0.567

The results of the hypothesis testing indicated that work conflict has a positive coefficient of 0.053; however, with a p-value of 0.765 (> 0.05), its effect on intention to quit is not statistically significant. Work overload also shows a positive relationship (coefficient = 0.257, p-value = 0.119), but also fails to reach significance at $\alpha = 0.05$. Work engagement has a negative coefficient of -0.251 (p-value = 0.147), indicating that higher work engagement is associated with lower intention to quit, although the relationship is not significant. The work environment, as a moderating variable, does not significantly strengthen or weaken the effect of work conflict (p-value = 0.284) or work overload (p-value = 0.567) on intention to quit. Thus, the work environment is not a significant moderator in this study.

D. Integration based on Qualitative Results (Interpretation)

Table 3. Integration

Theme	P-Value	Integration
Communication	0.765	The analysis of work conflicts confirmed the existence of "poor communication" with top management, between divisions, and external parties, although in the quantitative P value there

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		was no influence on the intention to quit, but in the results of the qualitative analysis with informants who had made the intention to quit, there was an influence through "poor communication" which slowly made employees make the intention to quit	Work Environment based on work atmosphere to Communication		The work environment in the agency cannot moderate work conflict towards the intention to quit quantitatively, but in the results through qualitative analysis there is a strong theme from the analysis of informant interviews, namely the work environment becomes "Environmental conditions based on the atmosphere" where if the environmental atmosphere is conducive then no conflict is triggered but if the environmental atmosphere is not conducive then conflicts between divisions, external and management levels occur more and more and allow this to reach the employee's personal problems so that the intention to quit work is getting bigger, although gradually.
Overload	0.119	The excessive workload analysis confirmed that the agency applied "overtime & excessive workload" to employees who were able to work even though their divisions were different. Quantitatively, the P value showed no effect on intention to quit, but qualitative results based on the analysis of informants who experienced this, with the theme of "excessive workload," did point to employees' intention to quit.		0.284	
Employee engagement with management person and external parties	0.147	Based on quantitative data, it can be seen that the P value of the work engagement variable does not have an effect on reducing the intention to change jobs simultaneously, but the results of qualitative analysis based on informant interviews stated that work engagement only makes employees freer to leave the institution and not close to management, across divisions, and external parties because it only creates new problems so that the intention to leave work becomes greater and more likely to be carried out.	Work Environment based on work atmosphere to overload	0.567	The work environment in the agency cannot moderate excessive workload on the intention to quit quantitatively, but qualitatively the results are the same as work environment conflict; if the atmosphere is conducive, then the excessive workload will not be felt, but on the contrary, if the work environment becomes non-conductive, then the workload will be increasingly felt and give rise to the desire to change jobs

Based on the results of the hypothesis test in Table 2, the Mixed Method can be combined through the interpretation table above. This coding demonstrates that contextual depth is necessary to understand the SEM-PLS model at AMN

Surabaya. Numerically, these factors are not strong enough to quantitatively alter the data, but psychologically, they are clearly perceived by informants within the organization.

Discussions

A. The Influence of Work Conflict on Turnover Intention

The findings indicate that work conflict has little impact on turnover intention, although a positive directional relationship was observed. Quantitative results indicate that current employees tend to avoid or withdraw from work conflict, thus reducing its measurable impact. However, qualitative data from former employees revealed that work conflict triggers a “work and leave” attitude, social withdrawal, and emotional exhaustion arising from dual leadership, persistent miscommunication, operational pressure, and bullying incidents. When work-related conflict is sensitive and lacks support from colleagues in the same division or internal management, employees’ turnover intention increases, reflecting disruptions to the fulfilment of social and self-esteem needs in Maslow (1943) hierarchy of needs. Thus, although work conflict is not statistically significant in predicting turnover intention in the structural model, qualitatively, work conflict serves as a psychological barrier that weakens employees’ sense of belonging and recognition, thereby increasing their likelihood of turnover. This pattern is consistent with the findings of Basinung et al. (2025), who also found that work conflict is insignificant but positively oriented towards turnover intention.

B. The Effect of Work Overload on Turnover Intention

The results showed that excessive workload contributed but did not have a significant impact on intention to quit. Quantitative data revealed that the “Working Conditions” indicator scored highest, indicating that AMN Surabaya employees frequently received workloads exceeding their normal working hours, but considered them normal and accepted as part of their duties. Qualitative analysis through interviews further strengthened these findings by indicating that excessive workload was triggered by overlapping job descriptions, poor coordination with superiors (manager/director), cross-divisional assignments, miscommunication, and additional tasks beyond job descriptions without breaks, resulting in a continuous and physically and mentally exhausting work rhythm. Limited environmental support accelerated burnout and led to offers of other jobs as an alternative to quitting. Although quantitatively, excessive workload did not appear to be the dominant factor, qualitative results indicated that excessive workload still played a role as a trigger for emotional stress, work-life imbalance, and relatively toxic work dynamics, potentially driving long-term intention to quit, particularly through the risk of burnout. Conceptually, this condition aligns with Maslow (1943) hierarchy of needs theory, where the fulfilment of basic needs such as salary and job stability can be balanced with a reasonable workload. However, if the workload is excessive and exceeds capacity, fulfilling

these needs becomes meaningless and strengthens the intention to quit. This finding is also in line with (Cahyanto and Julindrastuti, 2022), who found that excessive workload did not significantly affect intention to quit, although the direction of the relationship was positive, indicating a high tolerance for excessive workload as a consequence of the position. However, managerial interventions such as task redistribution, improved communication, and leadership training are still needed to prevent the subjective impact and long-term risks of burnout.

C. The Influence of Job Embeddedness on Turnover Intention

The results of this study indicated that job embeddedness has a weak influence and does not significantly contribute to turnover intention at AMN Surabaya. Quantitatively, the strongest indicator lies in the relatedness dimension. However, the pattern of inter-divisional relationships that tend to be exclusive and the formation of groups (cliques) actually reduces the strength of job embeddedness as a barrier to turnover intention, so that increasing psychological attachment is not strong enough to reduce turnover intention. Qualitative findings explain that excessive workloads without adequate compensation, flexible contract employee status, and internal conflict weaken the role of job embeddedness in maintaining retention. Informants also emphasized that monotonous work routines and limited work-life balance make job embeddedness less resilient in preventing employees from seeking experience or careers outside the agency. Theoretically, this condition aligns with Maslow (1943) hierarchy of needs, where failure to meet basic needs such as security and work-life balance hinders the formation of loyalty even though social ties and work relationships still exist. These results align with Risaldy and Ananda (2022), who found that external factors, such as more attractive financial offers and the career dynamics of the younger generation, are often more dominant in determining employee turnover decisions than job embeddedness. Thus, AMN Surabaya management needs to prioritize fulfilling basic needs and improving the work ecosystem before expecting long-term stability, loyalty, and career commitment from employees.

D. The Influence of Work Conflict on Turnover Intention Moderated by the Work Environment

The results of this study indicated that the work environment does not act as a moderator in the relationship between work conflict and intention to quit at AMN Surabaya. Quantitatively, there is no evidence that work environment dynamics strengthen or weaken the influence of work conflict on intention to quit, so that work conflict has a direct influence without being mediated by the environment. Qualitative findings from three informants revealed that the work environment actually exacerbates

conflict through task shifting, misunderstandings, and toxic inter-divisional dynamics, thus acting more as a trigger than a stabilizer. Support from colleagues in the same division is perceived to only partially reduce stress, but is insufficient to change intention to quit when the conflict is rooted in poor leadership structures and communication. This contradicts the research of Heryanto et al. (2024) which found a moderating role of the work environment, but is consistent with Maslow (1943) theory that failure to meet the needs for security and interpersonal relationships causes the work environment to lose its buffering function. Therefore, AMN Surabaya management needs to prioritize resolving structural conflicts and communication between levels and divisions, rather than solely managing facilities and the work environment.

E. The Effect of Work Overload on Turnover Intention Moderated by the Work Environment

The results of this study indicated that the work environment does not play a role as a moderator in the relationship between excessive workload and intention to quit work at AMN Surabaya. Quantitatively, excessive workload directly increases physical and mental fatigue, which leads to intention to quit, without being influenced by strengthening or weakening the work environment. Qualitative findings indicated that, although the work environment can provide comfort, excessive workload remains the main driver of the decision to quit, while verbal pressure and interaction dynamics in the environment only exacerbate the situation without changing the intensity of the intention to quit. The work environment is actually part of the pressure, not a counterbalance, in line with Maslow (1943) theory that basic needs such as rest and health must be met before environmental comfort can effectively prevent employee turnover. Thus, excessive workload is a dominant independent factor, while the work environment only plays a secondary and insignificant role in moderating employee intention to quit, especially in the context of an unbalanced division of tasks and staffing.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The mixed methods analysis in this research in an integrative manner produces comprehensive findings, which examined the influence of work conflict, work overload, and work engagement on employee turnover intentions, with the work environment as a moderating variable, namely:

1. Work conflict, a distinct theme, was identified through robust analysis of three informants, as leading to poor communication, which can increase misunderstandings between employees within or across divisions, as well as internal and external leaders, leading to a gradual but persistent decline in turnover intentions. Misunderstandings or misinformation in communication alone can hinder optimal work performance.

2. Work overload, which is less conducive to turnover intentions, may be due to employees' high tolerance for it, allowing them to directly prevent it. However, employees also experience physical exhaustion due to excessive workload. Without support, exhaustion can worsen over time. This was predicted through interviews, where the main theme from three informants was that excessive workload can reduce motivation, leading to intentions to quit, even if only a gradual but persistent increase over the years.

3. Attachment to Work: Consistent with theory, in-depth interviews revealed that the theme of "attachment to leadership and external factors" contributed to a high intention to quit. Other reinforcing factors included work conflict (communication), work overload (additional tasks requiring excellence but not rewarded), lack of career advancement, and an imbalance of equal pay and duties, making the intention to leave a highly desirable decision.

4. Moderating Work Environment: Work conflict and work overload did not moderate the intention to quit because both could directly influence the intention to quit, as did work overload, without being reinforced or weakened by the work environment. This was evident in the qualitative results from three informants, which indicated that the work environment was part of the "toxic" atmosphere and drama that occurred at the agency.

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